

GenOnet: Generative Open xG Network Simulation with Multi-Agent LLM and ns-3

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Abstract—The move toward Sixth-Generation (6G) networks relies on open interfaces and protocols for seamless interoperability across devices, vendors, and technologies. In this context, open 6G development involves multiple disciplines and requires advanced simulation approaches for testing. In this demo paper, we propose a *generative simulation* approach based on a multi-agent Large Language Model (LLM) and network simulator 3 (ns-3), called *Generative Open xG Network Simulation (GenOnet)*, to effectively generate, debug, execute, and interpret simulated Open Fifth-Generation (5G) environments. The first version of GenOnet application represents a specialized adaptation of the OpenAI GPT models. It incorporates supplementary tools, agents, 5G standards, and seamless integration with ns-3 simulation capabilities, supporting both C++ variants and Python implementations. This release complies with the latest Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) and 3GPP standards.

Index Terms—Open 5G/6G, multi-agent LLM, generative simulation, ns-3

I. INTRODUCTION

6G focuses on implementing open interfaces and protocols to ensure smooth interoperability across various devices, vendors, and technologies [1], [2]. In this intent, conducting a full-stack assessment of 6G cellular networks is crucial in determining the feasibility of any novel proposed approach for the next generation of wireless communication networks. 6G networks will incorporate a range of cutting-edge technologies at different levels, such as terahertz (THz) communication, network management driven by Artificial Intelligence (AI), Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN), and systems based on Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs). Performance bottlenecks can occur at any level of the network stack, potentially impacting the Quality of Service (QoS) for the entire system. Full-stack analysis is a method used to assess the performance and interaction of various technologies across all layers, ranging from the physical to the application layer. This analysis ensures that the technologies work together smoothly and that potential problems can be detected and resolved early. The main reason for the necessity of full-stack analysis across all layers is the unique characteristics of the underlying millimeter wave (mmWave) and sub-THz channels that have significant effects on the entire protocol stack [3]. For instance, the complexity of various essential procedures at the Medium Access Control (MAC) layer, such as synchronization, control signaling,

Figure 1: The graphical user interface of GenOnet application.

cell search, and initial access, is increased by using highly directional beams. This has an impact on both the system's robustness and delay. Another example is to validate O-RAN eXtended applications (xApps), it is crucial to enable the analysis of O-RAN use cases, such as Traffic Steering (TS) for load balancing users across cells and QoS for managing bearer parameters. These scenarios should involve the utilization of interactions and patterns as multiple User Equipments (UEs) interact with all layers of the network [4].

Insufficient access to testbeds for validating full-stack performance metrics can impede the confirmation of the applicability of novel proposed methods by researchers and developers for next-generation wireless communication networks. This constraint can potentially impede progress in the correct direction and mislead research and development. Discrete-event network simulators are a great alternative to evaluate performance, especially considering the limited availability of real 6G and beyond 5G (in particular Frequency Range (FR)2 and FR3) network deployments [5]. Discrete-event network simulators, such as ns-3¹, are crucial and commonly used tools for analyzing complex networks and developing new protocols. The ns-3 can accurately model several wireless and wired technologies, such as Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi) (built-in), 5G-LENA (for 5G-New Radio (NR), add-on)², and Terasim (for THz communication, add-on)³, as well as the Transmission

¹<https://www.nsnam.org/>

²<https://5g-lena.cttc.es/>

³<https://apps.nsnam.org/app/thz/>

Control Protocol (TCP)/IP protocol stack and applications. Notably, the ns-3 can accurately simulate the entire network stack, encompassing all layers and applications that function within the network. This makes ns-3 a great candidate for both research and industrial purposes.

Although ns-3 provides researchers and developers with features to implement and evaluate their methods comprehensively, dealing with ns-3 can be challenging. The user must have extensive knowledge of all network layers, along with a proficient understanding of object-oriented programming (particularly the C++ programming language) and specific standards such as 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), O-RAN, and Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE). The combination of these skills poses many challenges to make the most of the advantages of ns-3.

Innovative approaches become essential as the importance of LLMs grows, driven by the demand for advanced agents capable of reasoning, utilizing tools, and adapting to complex real-world environments like 5G/6G networks. We propose GenOnet as a novel approach to address the challenges associated with the complexity of utilizing ns-3 for open 5G/6G network simulations. It leverages advanced Generative AI techniques and multi-agent LLM to automate the generation, debugging, execution, and interpretation of simulated network environments without requiring extensive programming expertise or deep knowledge of network architectures and standards. Indeed, GenOnet effectively reduces the barriers to conducting advanced open xG network simulations. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Sec. II, we describe the main features of GenOnet. In Sec. III, we provide examples of use cases for GenOnet, which we showcase as demonstrations. Sec. IV concludes the work with suggestions for future research.

II. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

Figure 1 shows the GenOnet application’s graphical user interface. This application integrates several advanced tools and models in a user-friendly application using Streamlit⁴. GenOnet emphasizes modular design using LangChain⁵ and LangGraph⁶, allowing different agents to handle specific tasks, including information retrieval based on Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) technique, simulation generation, code execution, debugging, and interpretation. The questions and prompts in Figure 1 illustrate that the GenOnet framework is designed with user experience in mind, providing a smooth interface with dynamic updates and detailed feedback on the operations performed. The following is a technical analysis of how this application operates:

The GenOnet processes queries through a chain-based sequence, where each step involves a call to an LLM, a tool, or a data preprocessing task. The technical workflow of the provided application starts with input handling, where the application

⁴<https://streamlit.io>

⁵<https://www.langchain.com>

⁶<https://www.langchain.com/langgraph>

The image shows a code editor with C++ code for a network simulation. The code includes headers for ns-3, the 5G-LENA NR helper, and the UMi channel model. It defines a class for the simulation, sets up the network topology, and configures the TCP and channel models. The code is well-commented and includes a detailed explanation of the code at the bottom.

Figure 2: An example of simulation generation for TCP using the 5G-LENA NR helper with the 3GPP standards such as the urban microcells (UMi) channel model.

receives input from the user through the chat interface. Depending on the query type (e.g., regular query, C++/Python-based ns-3 generation, or ns-3 execution), the application routes the input to the appropriate processing component. Subsequently, prompt construction occurs, where the input is used to create a detailed and context-specific prompt, leveraging templates and dynamic variables. The constructed prompt is then forwarded to the LLM during the interaction phase, where the model processes the input and generates a response. Upon receiving the response, the application performs post-processing tasks, including executing generated code, debugging, interpreting outputs, and formatting the response. Memory management is implemented through Streamlit’s session state, which maintains the history of interactions, ensuring that the conversation context is preserved across multiple exchanges. Finally, in the output handling stage, the processed response is rendered in the chat interface, formatted with custom styling, and presented to the user, completing the interaction loop. This entire process is designed to operate seamlessly in real-time, providing the user with immediate feedback and dynamic updates.

III. EVALUATION

Figure 2 illustrates an instance of the simulation generator functionality of GenOnet. This feature enables the app to automatically generate simulation scripts in both Python and C++ programming languages. Despite being in its initial

```

Mean flow throughput:56.23260 Mean flow delay: 0.58857
Interpretation:
The output indicates the results of a network simulation or performance test involving two IP flows.

1. #Flow 1:
- #Transmitted (Tx): 5000 packets sent, totaling 768,000 bytes.
- #Received (Rx): 5000 packets received, totaling 768,000 bytes.
- #Throughput: 10.23 Mbps, which is slightly less than the offered load, indicating some packet loss.
- #Round Delay: 0.278 ms, which is the average time taken for packets to travel from sender to receiver.
- #Jitter: 0.000 ms, indicating the variability in packet delay.

2. #Flow 2:
- #Transmitted (Tx): 5000 packets sent, totaling 7,680,000 bytes.
- #Received (Rx): 5000 packets received, totaling 7,680,000 bytes.
- #Throughput: 100.23 Mbps, which is also slightly less than the offered load, indicating some packet loss.
- #Round Delay: 0.268 ms, which is higher than flow 1, suggesting more congestion or delay in this flow.
- #Jitter: 0.120 ms, indicating a higher variability in packet delay compared to flow 1.

3. #Overall Statistics:
- #Mean Flow Throughput: 55.23 Mbps, which is an average of the throughput of both flows.
- #Mean Flow Delay: 0.588 ms, which is the average delay across both flows.

The results suggest that while both flows are functioning, there is some packet loss and variability in delay, which could be indicative of network congestion or other issues affecting performance.

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Figure 3: The experimentation shows the execution and interpretation of a setup simulation using the 3GPP channel model from TR 38.901 based on the 5G-Lena NR module.

development phase, the generator can produce ns-3 simulation scripts that offer users a thorough comprehension of the essential configuration procedures. Nevertheless, generating bug-free simulation scripts that can be compiled successfully remains challenging at this stage. Figure 2 shows the result for the prompt *"I want to use XR traffic with the 5G-Lena NR helper, which uses a 3GPP UMI channel model with a frequency of 28 GHz and a 200 MHz bandwidth and 1 component carrier with 100 UE's. Also, I want to have a TCP application and a scanning beamforming method."* The code structure of the generator closely adheres to the ns-3 C++ code examples. It includes the required header files, the ns-3 namespace, the NS_LOG_COMPONENT, the use of helpers, and the simulator Run/Destroy methods. Also, the code template demonstrates how to configure channel attributes such as frequency and bandwidth based on the user's input. The quantity of gNBs and UEs, as determined by the user prompt, has been precisely configured. The code generates sample code to configure the TCP protocol using the bulkSendHelper based on the user's prompt. The code generator indicates to the users that they have to do an attachment based on 5G-Lena Helper.

Figure 3 depicts the GenOnet app's response to running and interpreting ns-3 code. This configuration utilizes the 3GPP channel model from TR 38.901⁷, based on the 5G-Lena NR module⁸. The outcomes provide comprehensive performance metrics, including throughput, delay, and jitter for two User Datagram Protocol (UDP) flows. They showcase the effectiveness of the GenOnet in assessing network performance across different scenarios.

In Figure 4, we can observe a client-server communication scenario⁹ wherein the client transmits a 1024-byte packet to the server at time t=2 seconds. The server, located at IP address 10.1.2.4 on port 9, promptly receives the packet and sends back a response of equivalent size to the client at time

⁷<https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3173>

⁸https://gitlab.com/cttc-lena/nr/-/blob/master/examples/cttc-nr-demo.cc?ref_type=heads

⁹https://gitlab.com/nsnam/ns-3-dev/-/blob/master/examples/tutorial/second.py?ref_type=heads

```

address = ns.Ipv4AddressHelper(
    address.Subnet0(ns.Ipv4Address("10.1.1.0"), ns.Ipv4Mask("255.255.255.0"))(
        prefix=ns.AddressAssign(300Devices)
    ),
    address.Subnet1(ns.Ipv4Address("10.1.2.0"), ns.Ipv4Mask("255.255.255.0"))(
        prefix=ns.AddressAssign(300Devices)
    ),
    echoServer = ns.Ipv4EchoServerHelper(1)
)
serverApps = ns EchoServerInstall(
    comNodes.Get(1)(CmaValue)
)
serverApps.Start(
    ns.Second(1.0)
)
serverApps.Stop(
    ns.Second(10.0)
)
ns EchoClient = ns.Ipv4EchoClientHelper(
    comNodes.Get(1)(CmaValue),
    comNodes.Get(2)(CmaValue),
    ns EchoClient.SAMMIBuffer(
        "MaxPackets",
        ns.SetIntegerValue(1)
    ),
    ns EchoClient.SAMMIBuffer(
        "Interval",
        ns.SetIntegerValue(10)
    ),
    ns EchoClient.SAMMIBuffer(
        "Packetsize",
        ns.SetIntegerValue(1024)
    ),
    clientApps = ns EchoClientInstall(
        comNodes.Get(0)
    ),
    clientApps.Start(
        ns.Second(2.0)
    ),
    clientApps.Stop(
        ns.Second(10.0)
    ),
    ns.Ipv4GlobalRoutingHelper.PopulateRoutingTable(
        packet.EnablePopUpAll,
        "second",
        comNodes.Get(1),
        comNodes.Get(2)
    ),
    ns.Simulator.Run(
        ns.Simulator.Destroy()
    )

```

Output: At time t=2s client sent 1024 bytes to 10.1.2.4 port 9. At time t=2.0118s server received 1024 bytes from 10.1.1.1 port 49153. At time t=2.02161s client received 1024 bytes from 10.1.2.4 port 9.

Interpretation: The output describes a sequence of network communication events between a client and a server.

- At 2 seconds, the client sends a packet of 1024 bytes to the server located at IP address 10.1.2.4 on port 9.
- Shortly after, at 2.0118 seconds, the server receives the same packet of 1024 bytes from the client, which is identified by its IP address 10.1.1.1 and a source port of 49153.
- Immediately after receiving the packet, the server sends a response of 1024 bytes back to the client at the same source port (49153).
- Finally, at 2.02161 seconds, the client receives the 1024-byte response from the server at IP address 10.1.2.4 on port 9.

This sequence indicates a successful round-trip communication where the client sends a request, the server processes it, and then responds back to the client. The timestamps show the precise timing of each event, indicating a very short response time from the server.

Figure 4: Execution and interpretation of a Python-based ns-3 example.

t=2.0118 seconds. As explained in the interpretation, the client successfully receives the server's response at time t=2.02161 seconds, demonstrating efficient round-trip communication with precise timestamps.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this demo, we have presented the GenOnet framework, a novel and innovative approach to simulating open 5G/6G network environments by leveraging multi-agent LLMs and the ns-3. It provides a flexible platform for generating, debugging, executing, and interpreting network scenarios to advance next-generation network technologies. GenOnet integrates 5G standards and aligns with existing simulation tools, streamlining the testing and validation of open network architectures. Future developments will focus on expanding capabilities to accommodate full 5G/6G network simulations, including emerging standards and technologies. This will involve enhancements to the multi-agent LLM framework and integration of real-time data analytics and machine learning algorithms for adaptive and predictive network behaviors within the simulation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was partially funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 grant PID2021-126431OB-I00 (ANEMONE), Spanish MINECO grant TSI-063000-2021-54 (6G-DAWN ELASTIC) and grant TSI-063000-2021-56 (6G-BLUR SMART), and Generalitat de Catalunya grant 2021 SGR 00770.

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